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Executive summary

This document will outline the different performance values of the overall PHM architecture inside the test facility. Time dependent evolutions of certain plant health related values will be given and sources for disturbances/failures will be analyzed.

Table of contents

Executive summary 3

Table of contents 4

Acronyms 5

1 System Performance 6

1.1 General Imaging System 6

1.2 Dual Wavelength Spectral Imagers 12

1.3 Automated Remote ‘Plant Health Monitoring’ System 14

1.3.1 Method 14

1.3.2 Results 15

2 System Maintenance and Observed Issues 19

2.1 General Imaging System 19

2.2 Automated Remote ‘Plant Health Monitoring’ System 20

3 On-Site System Improvements 21

3.1 General Imaging System 21

3.2 Dual Wavelength Spectral Imagers 22

3.3 Automated Remote ‘Plant Health Monitoring’ System 23

4 Proposed Future System Improvements 24

4.1 General Imaging System 24

4.2 Dual Wavelength Spectral Imagers 24

4.3 Automated Remote ‘Plant Health Monitoring’ System 24

Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
BF	Blue Film	NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
DBP	Dual Band Pass filters	NM-III	Neumayer Station III
DLR	German Aerospace Center	PHM	Plant Health Monitoring
FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse	ROI	Region of Interest
HD	High Definition	SES	Service Section
HW	Hardware	SW	Software
IR	Infrared	TPZ	Telespazio
ISPR	International Standard Payload Rack	UF	University of Florida
LSDA	NASA's Life Sciences Data Archive	UFSI	UF Spectral Imaging
MCC	Mission Control Center	UHB	User Home Base
MTF	Mobile Test Facility		

1 System Performance

Overview of the subsystem performance during the Antarctic deployment phase.

1.1 General Imaging System

The Imaging System, as implemented in the FEG, is composed of several elements:

1. Fixed system of visual HD cameras, one for each/two trays, for the acquisition of **top-view** images,
2. Fixed system of visual HD cameras, two for each rack, for the acquisition of **lateral-view** images,
3. System to connect the cameras to the EDEN ISS network and
4. SW application for daily images acquisition, local storage and forwarding to the European sites.

Such a system has been implemented using the HIKVISION DS-2CD2542F-I 4MP cameras, used as follow:

- 17 are mounted on the ceiling of each rack level (with the exclusion of the nursery), pointing downward towards two trays for top view imaging,
- 7 are mounted on the ceiling of each nursery level (for the first to the third level, two per level/ one for each tray; for upper level one camera for the whole level), pointing downward towards the trays, for top view imaging and
- 8 are mounted along the corridor, on the rack structure pointing at the opposite rack for lateral view imaging.

Figure 1-1 gives an idea of the camera position as described in the above bullet lines.

Figure 1-1: Camera System Configuration.

The above described cameras are connected to the MTF network via Ethernet switches located in the FEG and the SES. In addition, they are controlled by a computer, named **Camera Control PC**, equipped with dedicated camera management SW.

Beside the possibility for the EDEN ISS operator on site to have a continuous streaming of data on the Camera-PC (MTF), and the possibility to record videos and take snapshots whenever needed, the imaging system is also managing the following tasks:

- Schedule a daily picture acquisition, for the TOP and SIDE view cameras, and store them on Camera-PC (MTF).
- Forward the pictures (TOP + SIDE VIEW) to the NM-III Antarctica Base and the EDEN ISS MCC @DLR Bremen.

That is done by ad-hoc developed SW applications based on the programming language **Python**. In particular the **camera_snapshot_robot.py** is the SW application for picture acquisition, while the **camera_ftp_robot_DLR.py** is taking care of the snapshot file ftp transfer to the OPS-PC at DLR site in Bremen. The **camera_ftp_robot_NMIII.py** is taking care of the snapshot file ftp transfer to the Camera-PC (NM-III) at NM-III where the image repository for backup purposes is located. These SW applications require the definition of several parameters, like for example the camera network parameters, the storage path, the destination path. These parameters are defined in the **hikvision.py** SW application that therefore is a sort of subroutine of the other applications.

In addition the following batch files manage in automatic way the storage path creation, the acquisition of the images and their distribution to the remote site, both DLR and NM-III:

- edeniss_mkdir.bat
- edeniss_remote_mkdir.bat
- edeniss_camera_scheduler_DLR.bat
- edeniss_camera_scheduler_NMIII.bat

In particular, **edeniss_mkdir.bat** and **edeniss_remote_mkdir.bat** create image directories following a predefined structure, respectively on local PCs at MTF (Camera-PC, Argus-PC and ISPR-PC) and on remote PCs at NM-III and DLR. The batch files **edeniss_camera_scheduler_DLR.bat** and **edeniss_camera_scheduler_NMIII.bat** are the applications that schedule the tasks for daily image acquisition for the TOP and SIDE view cameras, and ftp file transfer for the TOP and SIDE view cameras as well for the UFI imagers to the remote sites, both DLR and NM-III.

Anyway, the above listed SW applications are a part of a more complex SW suite that manages not only the HD images, but also the Argus Data, and the ISPR Data and images. Their description is out of the scope of this document and are provided, with in addition even more details on the Imaging system, in the document D3.11 – PHM Design Report [RD 1].

Figure 1-2 and Figure 1-3 provide a pictorial view of the camera network and of the image flows.

Figure 1-2: Camera Network.

Figure 1-3: Images and data flow.

The system has been configured to generate one image per camera and per day at around midnight. The images are saved in jpeg format and have a maximum size of approximately 400 kbyte, depending on the light conditions.

The images are saved in the following folders on both the Camera-PC (MTF) and the Camera PC (NM-III):

- *D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\HDTOPVIEW\<camera position1>*
 Where *<camera position1>* is:
 - L1-2C, L1-4C
 - L2-1C, L2-2C, L2-3C, L2-4C
 - L3-1C, L3-2C, L3-3C, L3-4C

- L4-1L, L4-2L, L4-3L
 - L4-1R, L4-2R, L4-3R, L4-4C
 - R1-2C, R1-4C
 - R2-2C, R2-4C
 - R3-4C
 - R4-2C, R4-4C
- *D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\HDSIDEVIEW<camera position2>*
 Where *<camera position2>* is:
 - L12-1S, L12-3S, L34-1S, L34-3S
 - R12-1S, R12-3S, R34-1S, R34-3S

The images are saved using this naming convention: HDCam_<cameraposition>_<date>_<time>, with the date expressed in yearmonthday (yyyymmdd), and the time expressed in hourminute (hhmm).

This structure is then replicated on the OPS-PC (DLR EDEN ISS MCC), which is the final repository of all the images and data generated in the MTF at the Antarctica site. As already said, the system has been designed and realized with the capability to automatically send the images to DLR after the images acquisition activity has been completed.

One user of the images is the University of Wageningen, which uses the images for plant health monitoring. The access to the images is done via ftp secure connection to the DLR OPS-PC. Once available at the University of Wageningen, the images are processed with a dedicated SW to assess the plants status in order to provide a forecast of the harvesting date and, most of all, to early detect possible problems and define corrective or even medical actions in the early stage of the plant sickness. Other project participants can get the access privileges and download images for other purposes, e.g. Telespazio is downloading pictures in its role as the responsible entity for the Imaging System itself.

The following pictures describes how the ftp server is organised, from the higher level (Figure 1-4), to the single folder content (Figure 1-6).

Figure 1-4: Ftp Server Structure.

Figure 1-5: HD Top View images folder structure.

Figure 1-6: Single folder content (L3-3C content).

From the start of the operations to date (12 October 2018), including the commissioning phase, 273 images (≈ 85 Mbyte) have been taken from each camera, adding up to a total of 8736 images ($\approx 2,8$ Gbyte) for the entire MTF. The following figures show an example of daily taken pictures:

Figure 1-7: Top View - L2-1C camera.

Figure 1-8: Top View - L3-3C camera.

Figure 1-9: Top View - R3-4C camera.

Figure 1-10: Side View – R3/4-3S.

1.2 Dual Wavelength Spectral Imagers

The University of Florida seeks to bring to the EDEN project expertise and experience in plant growth in spaceflight environments, along with spaceflight experience in using specific informative imaging capabilities. In particular the UF team will develop dual wavelength Spectral Imagers and imaging procedures within the EDEN ISS facilities and provide image processing and analysis during the deployment phase of the project.

This UF part of the project brings established research from NASA-funded science on the International Space Station into an international project led by DLR toward the functionalization of plant growth in support of human exploration. Imaging technologies developed as part of ongoing ISS science will

be deployed within the Antarctic EDEN ISS plant production unit to provide tele-science support and plant science analytics to better understand the responses of plants to extreme environments and off nominal growth situations, and production support to optimize plant performance.

In the first year of operations (2018), UF produced prototype imagers based on the GoPro commercial cameras and assisted in the final installation setup at the Neumayer III Antarctic site at the start of the project run. The first generation of UF Spectral Imaging cameras were based on the GoPro Hero4. They were modified to allow near IR into the sensor and a dual wavelength filter to collect both red and Near IR and the Red pixels of the sensor, while green and blue wavelengths are captured by the Green and Blue pixels. The filter blocks all greenish yellow, yellow and orange wavelengths to offer clear separation of the informative wavelengths to the image sensor. The modifications are enabled through the use of the Back-Bone Ribcage mod kit. The resulting images can be easily separated using plugins for ImageJ or other software, and the separated images can be manipulated by pixel math to produce normalized differential images using a wide range of pixel mathematics. Using a single sensor and single filter keeps the visible and near IR images in perfect register, eliminates the need for a mechanical filter wheels in the camera, and keeps the number of images that have to be managed by the data system to a minimum. Figure 1-12 shows a summary of the UF Spectral Imaging (UFSI) system set up.

Figure 1-11: The basic steps involved in the assembly and deployment of the UF Spectral Imaging (UFSI) GoPro system (A), and an example of images captured in healthy and salt-stressed plants (B).

In the 2018 season UF monitored plant health with the modified GoPros, and the images were used in laboratory analyses, as well as being archived in NASA's Life Sciences Data Archive (LSDA), and used for educational and public outreach work. The operational model is that UFSI data would provide an additional layer of plant health monitoring, which would then inform operators of any potential areas of concern (Figure 1-12 A). For example, in May of 2018, there was a problem in the nutrient delivery system for one of the trays of tomato plants. From a distance, there was no discernable difference in the appearance of the tomatoes, but the UFSI images showed a quantitative decline in plant health (Figure 1-12 B). Analyses of the entire 2018 image data set is ongoing.

Figure 1-12: (A) The basic information path that was envisioned for the UFSI system integrated into the FEG. (B) An example from May of 2018 where the UFSI system recorded an anomaly in the health of one of the trays of tomato plants in the FEG.

1.3 Automated Remote ‘Plant Health Monitoring’ System

The Business Unit Greenhouse Horticulture of Wageningen Research developed an automated system for remote ‘plant health monitoring’, based on the image acquisition system described above (see chapter 1.1). The monitoring system warns when growth rates decline or other anomalies are registered, and predicts harvest time. In this chapter the monitoring system is described and examples of 2 lettuce cultivars (Batavia and Expertise) are presented.

1.3.1 Method

In the FEG, 24 top view HD cameras (RGB cameras) were installed above the trays and once per day a picture of the trays with plants was taken (Figure 1-13 right). As said above, the images were daily automatically downloaded and sent to Wageningen. The image of the tray was divided in 4 sectors (roughly, but not necessarily, one per plant) and the “region of interest” (ROI) was selected by an algorithm based on the RGB pixels (Figure 1-13 left).

Figure 1-13: Image of lettuce plants in a tray. Image on the right is the original image and on the left is the image after the first processing: the tray is divided in 4 sectors (blue), and region of interest (ROI in red) is defined.

The region of interest per sector was used for early detection of anomalies, through comparison with the data of the previous day, and for the evaluation of performance of the crop. For the ‘early detection’ of anomalies, decrease in apparent leaf area (above a threshold) and changes in RGB ratios were used. Upon detection of such anomalies a ‘hard warning’ was generated by sending an automated e-mail which included a description of the anomaly and a link to the pictures leading to the warning (actual and previous). The procedure relied on an “administration file” maintained on Antarctica, about transplanting and harvesting of each tray.

The rate of increase of the ROI was used for the prediction of harvest time, and the evaluation of crop performance. The latter was done through comparison with earlier performances of the same crop. If the performance was not satisfactory, a ‘soft warning’ was included in the e-mail with ‘hard warnings’ and the decline in performance was mentioned (as %) and a plot of the extrapolated growth (and the previous, better one) was included.

1.3.2 Results

Early detection (hard warning)

“Hard” warnings were sent often and were visually checked by experts at Wageningen University & Research by comparing the images of the day. The hard warning was defined and the day before image using the link to the images included in the mail message. During the cultivation period in the FEG from March to November 2018, virtually all “hard warnings” were caused by untimely registration of harvest event on Antarctica. A few were caused by natural causes, such a varying orientation of leaves (it can affect significantly ROI, particularly in young plants), and could easily be dismissed by the experts. In short, no direct actions had to be taken based on the automated image acquisition system during the cultivation in the FEG. This was also the experience of the grower at Antarctica, who never reported severe crop problems for these lettuce crops. Nevertheless, in order to test the system, we asked him to generate artificially a “hard warning”, by “mistreating a few leaves. The anomaly was timely detected, thus we deem the system accurate enough, provided the administration on-site is timely.

Prediction of harvest time

The daily increase in the ROI area was used to predict number of days to full soil cover. Expert knowledge was used about time thereafter to harvest. It was calculated that one week after transplanting, harvest day could be predicted within +/- two days.

Evaluation of crop performance (soft warning)

Predicted growth rates were not very variable: standard deviation of prediction among the different cycles was 8.5% for Batavia and 6.6% for Expertise. Indeed, as in the FEG all climate and root zone factors were kept constant among cycles and there were no pathologies, comparable growth rates among different crop cycles of the same species had to be expected.

Nevertheless, the variation in fresh weight among various cycles was larger: 25% to 30%, see Table 1-1 which shows production of the different cultivation cycles. Therefore it is a reasonable question whether the system performed well enough.

Table 1-1: production of edible and total biomass of 6 lettuce plants per tray (g fresh weight/tray) in different cultivation cycles (batches 1-18). Batches 2 and 16 are excluded, on the advice of the grower on Antarctica (Paul Zabel).

Batch	Harvest date	Cycle length (days)	Batavia		Expertise	
			Edible FW (g/tray)	Total FW (g/tray)	Edible FW (g/tray)	Total FW (g/tray)
1	20-3-2018	41	539.5	743.8	637.8	875.6
2	3-4-2018	33				
3	19-4-2018	35	456.6	639.3	768.7	953.3
4	3-5-2018	37	678.7	902.7	817.5	1081.3
5	16-5-2018	38	605.9	795.9	730	928.7
6	29-5-2018	38	620.9	839.1	806.5	1005.7
7	13-6-2018	35	335.8	493.8	611.9	799.6
8	26-6-2018	42	806.2	1065.8	1147.8	1497.5
9	11-7-2018	35	207.5	378.8	365.6	467.8
10	31-7-2018	35	322.4	511.1	492.5	677.2
11	10-8-2018	37	498.2	701	843.8	1077.6
12	27-8-2018	39	673.6	906.3	1079.9	1355.7
13	7-9-2018	38	589.3	809.7	889.3	1138.4
14	24-9-2018	39	515.5	760.1	902.2	1184.3
15	8-10-2018	39	527.7	740.1	978.3	1273
16	21-10-2018	37				
17	3-11-2018	38	369.7	549	623.4	808.4
18	20-11-2018	39	453	655.7	799.9	1015.7

There is a very high correlation between edible and total fresh weight, Figure 1-14, so that we can limit the analysis to any of the two.

Figure 1-14: Total fresh weight production (g/tray) in different cultivation cycles of Batavia and Expertise vs edible fresh weight.

The most obvious factor for production differences (once climate, nutrition and pathologies are excluded) are cycle length and plant size at the moment of transplanting. Indeed, cycle length (maximum difference between cycle length is 7 days) proved a reasonable predictor of fresh weight (Figure 1-15).

Figure 1-15: Total fresh weight production (g/tray) in 16 different cultivation cycles of Batavia and Expertise with different cycle lengths.

We then selected a sub-set of cycles (37, 38 and 39 days) that reduced the correlation between cycle length and fresh weight to nihil. The standard deviation of final fresh weight of the cycles in that sub-

set was reduced to 15% and there was no correlation between plant size at transplanting and final fresh weight.

It has to be said that fresh weight is known to be much more variable than dry weight: for instance time of harvest after start of “day” can affect it, so that it is debatable that a variation of 15% is significant.

In short, we do not have enough information (or we did not create enough variation) to judge the reliability of this part (the “soft” warning) of the PHM system.

2 System Maintenance and Observed Issues

Description of regular maintenance protocols (all as planned or some surprises?). What failures or issues arose within the system during the Antarctic deployment phase?

2.1 General Imaging System

In principle, no particular maintenance is required for the Imaging System, and only minor issues have been experienced during the operations. However, before listing them, it is worth to spend some words on the early phase of the operations and of the commissioning phase.

The fine tuning of the system has required some interaction between the Antarctica operators and the Telespazio UHB, in its role of Support Center for the Imaging System.

Upon request to put the quality of the captured images to high and of the video to low quality, and to increase the image size, some test have been done to correctly configure the system using the Imaging System Test Platform in the Telespazio Lab. The test platform allows configuring the system and/or testing different camera configurations. Moreover it can simulate the end-to-end image flows, being composed, apart the cameras and the switch, of three PC's, simulating respectively the FEG, the NM-III and the DLR MCC.

These activities have led to the definition of the camera's configuration parameters to be used during the operation as follow:

Stream Type = Main Stream
Bitrate Type = Variable
Video Quality = Highest
Frame Type = P
IFrame Internal = 50
Video Encoding = Medium
Bitrate = 4096
Resolution = 2688x1520
Frame Rate = 1/16
Video Encoding = H.264
SVC = Auto

The testing activities helped also resolving/understanding a discrepancy on the images size:

1. The same images acquired manually (snapshot) using the Hikvision SW, and using the Telespazio SW application was showing a different size (≈ 600 vs ≈ 400 kbyte),
2. The image size, even if acquired at the maximum resolution, was always less of the 2 MB used or calculation during the design phase.

As result of the test, and with the HIKVISION support, for the first point we have learned that the discrepancy stands on the different way the HIKVISION SW and the Telespazio SW work. The first adds some metadata to the images to allow its processing by the SW itself, the second is acquiring a pure images. Therefore a discrepancy in the size is normal.

As far as the second point is concerned, the test helped in further understanding the behaviour and capacity of the camera system.

In particular each camera can acquire **not compressed (bmp)** or **compressed (jpg)**. The not compressed images can reach a size that is largely exceeding the 2 Mbyte used for calculation. The size depends on the resolution, and for example using the maximum resolution it possible can get **bmp images** at 16 Mbyte. This 16 Mbyte are reduced to the approximately 400 kbyte, if the images are

compressed to the **jpg format**. This compression does not affect the quality of the images, since a jpg file format has the capability to analyse which information is important for a particular image, discarding what is not important. That makes unidentifiable changes to the image, which cannot be distinguished by the human eye, with a significant reduction of the file size to more than 1/20th of the original file size.

Therefore the possibility to acquire jpg images is not affecting the Wageningen experts capability to process the images, and on the other hand gives clear advantages.

A first benefit stands on the fact that there are less data to be transferred, and therefore the transfer process of the images, that has to face a strong limitation on the band, is less demanding of what expected. A second benefit stands on the fact that there are still rooms for a system update with more powerful cameras, and with the final objective to improve even more the quality of the images.

However, the TPZ SW can capture jpg images only. This limitation is coming from the HIKVISION protocol that presently does not provide instruction for external users on how to acquire bmp images.

Apart from what was described above, other minor issues have been resolved as described below:

- Acquisition of images without the timestamp and the camera location: That occurred not more than two times, the root cause is not known, but the recovery action is known and works,
- Scratches on the camera cover glass: Solved replacing the cover with a new one (cover available because acquired after that a similar incident occurred during the integration phase in Bremen. As matter of fact the side view camera's protrude in the corridor and can be easily touched and damaged) and
- Replacement of a 2 MP, camera mounted by mistake, with a 4 MP camera.

2.2 Automated Remote 'Plant Health Monitoring' System

Once following a learning curve the ROI is well detected no additional effort is needed. In case a new crop is added in the cropping system the detection of the ROI has to be adapted with new settings for this crop. Reliability of automated systems like this stands or falls by the same circumstances. Displacement of the camera positions, exact placement of the trays in the racks and the light conditions at the moment the photo is taken must be as equal as possible. Only a few times there have been such deviations that this led to false warnings. For these seldom occasions the software isn't adapted.

Especially reflections from other sources as the structure of the FEG on leaves and fruits can influence the defined ROI. This occurred for other crops than the analysed Batavia and Expertise when a maintenance trolley was placed in the FEG at the moment the daily pictures were taken. Harvest of the crop from a tray below the tray at the image can result in a lower region of interest and lead to a false hard warning. In case each tray is placed in a complete enclosed box no influence of other crops (side or below) can occur. Now it's assumed and in practice variation will be limited, the light intensity during the crop cycle on a specific tray is constant. The light intensity at crop level is not always exact the same due to the influence of other crops next to the observed tray. For example the light intensity at crop level of 2 different growth cycles of lettuce was probably influenced by the increase in height of the pepper plants next to the tray and can influence the crop growth.

Harvesting the crop without direct (the same day) administration in a file at Antarctica can result in a false hard warning.

3 On-Site System Improvements

How was the system improved on-site out of necessity or reasons of ‘nice-to-have’ improvements? What operational lessons were learned that could improve future operations?

3.1 General Imaging System

Based on the possibility to have high quality jpg images with small size, it has been decided to upgrade the imaging system with more powerful cameras. That was done during the visit to the Antarctica site planned for January 2019.

The requirements for the selection of a new camera have been derived from two main facts:

- Wish to improve the imaging system capabilities as much as possible and
- Need to minimize the effort in SW and HW upgrade, trying to use the existing interfaces as well as the existing SW applications as they are.

Based on that the 8 MP HIKVISION DS-2CD2185FWD-I(S) has been selected (see Figure 3-16). This camera on one hand doubles the maximum resolution of the cameras presently installed in the FEG, on the other hand it has the same capabilities of the already used cameras in terms of power/data interface, operating conditions, power consumptions. The capability to be used with the same SW applications as developed for the previous camera has been demonstrated by test as described in the next lines.

Figure 3-16: 4 MP (left) and 8 MP (right) cameras.

One camera has been acquired and installed in the test setup in the Telespazio lab to test its functionalities and verify its compatibility with the already deployed system.

Figure 3-17: Test Setup in the Telespazio lab.

Two tests have been conducted, from September 7th to 14th 2018, with two objectives:

- Demonstrating the possibility to use the selected camera, and to find out the configuration parameters and the installation procedure and
- Verifying the capability of the system to automatically acquire and transfer the images as expected.

Both tests were successful. In particular the second test has been conducted continuously for 5 days with the acquisition of several images, more than one per day, and demonstrated the capability of the new camera's to work exactly as the system is presently working in the MTF at NM-III.

As result of the test, the go for the acquisition of the new camera model has been given to DLR, and the procedure for the new camera installation has been prepared and provided as well.

The new camera model is a little bigger than the already used camera, and in principle it cannot be used in all the locations. For this reason it has been decided to replace only a subset of the cameras and in particular only those far from the target. Therefore the cameras for lateral view and those for top view for the tall and medium plants (like for example tomatoes, pepper, and cucumber), which in the early stage of plant growth are far away from the cameras resulting in poor details definition, have been replaced. Following this approach, only 17 cameras (out of 32) were replaced as listed below:

Top View

L1 2C, L1 4C, R1 2C, R1 4C, R2 2C, R2 4C, R3 4C, R4 2C, R4 4C,

Side view

L12-1S, L12-3S, L34-1S, L34-3S, R12-1S, R12 -3S, R34-1S, R34-3S.

Those for nursery and for the short plants were kept unchanged.

3.2 Dual Wavelength Spectral Imagers

In 2019 UF recalibrated some of the original GoPro cameras and also modified and installed six new cameras based on the Hikvision network cameras being used as part of the other PHM system in the FEG. Modifications were done at NM-III. Figure 3-18 illustrates some of the operations that the modifications entailed (Figure 3-18 A overview, B-D stages of disassembly).

Three different filters were used:

1. **NDVI-7** – the original NDVI filter. These are thin and small enough to fit in-frame with the existing housing, and could be set in place with a dot of super glue
2. New Dual Band Pass filters (**DBP**) – These are round, thick glass with optical coatings. These round filters were about 1 mm too wide to fit perfectly into the Hikvision camera framework, so one edge was ground down with a steel file to enable a flush fit. Filter was secured with dots of super glue on edges (Figure 3-18 E).
3. Blue film (**BF**) – an economical option suitable for educational outreach applications; schools could easily purchase and adapt these filters, also easily cut to fit with scissors.

After the filters secured and glue dry, the cameras were individually focused before the cameras were reassembled into their housing.

Figure 3-18: Modification of the Hikvision cameras in 2019 at NM-III. (A) Overview, (B-D) various stages of disassembly, (E) modification of the DBP glass filter.

The UF cameras were installed in six different locations throughout the FEG to monitor a variety of crops (Figure 3-19). The Hikvision deployment of the original NDVI-7 filter is being compared to the new DBP filter in Hikvision cameras by using both to observe the same tray of plants (bush tomatoes in L1).

As of the time of this report, there are no crops being grown in the FEG.

Figure 3-19: 2019 Layout of the cameras in the FEG (left) and installation (right).

3.3 Automated Remote 'Plant Health Monitoring' System

No improvements on site were done.

4 Proposed Future System Improvements

What could improve the system in a step-wise manner? Any major ideas that should be described if the system would be completely redesigned?

4.1 General Imaging System

The system is working pretty well; nevertheless, some improvements could be considered. One improvement could be on the HW side, with HD cameras designed ad hoc for Plant Health monitoring, with some functions developed ad hoc for plant imaging, and without all the functions that are common to all the cameras designed and developed for ambient monitoring. It could be useful for example to have smaller camera integrated in LED panel and with higher resolution than the 8 MP which were implemented. The SW developed for the EDEN ISS operations, even if working perfectly, appears not to be so user friendly. It has to be used by a killed operator. An effort to improve the usability of such a SW application could be taken into account for future development.

4.2 Dual Wavelength Spectral Imagers

Until now there are no future improvements of the system planned.

4.3 Automated Remote 'Plant Health Monitoring' System

Luckily, the conditions in the FEG and the quality of the operations team made a "plant health monitoring" system, in fact, unnecessary. Nevertheless, future Antarctica or deep space missions may not be so lucky. In addition, there is a growing need for such "intelligent" systems also in terrestrial production, such as in "vertical farms" or high tech greenhouses. It is thus good to consider possible improvements:

- The "hard warning" proved to be reliable. Reliability strongly depends on an accurate crop administration while most hard warnings were caused by an inaccurate (at the moment of processing the pictures) administration. Increasing the diagnostic power of the system by first testing an "expert list" of hypothesis on the cause of the detection and afterwards creating a "hard warning" can reduce hard warnings significantly. Only thereafter a warning, requiring expert analysis should be generated.
- The prediction of harvest time was not really necessary, as there was a dedicated grower in this mission. It may be more useful whenever an untrained crew has to plan activities in the greenhouse.
- There was no real test of the predictor of crop performance (the "soft warning"). Before considering improvements (whether for future missions or terrestrial applications) we would need to test the system by creating artificially conditions leading to sub-optimal crop performance.